

PHONETICS AS A BRANCH OF LINGUISTICS

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Abstract. *This article is dedicated to the theme "Phonetics as a branch of linguistic" as well as one of the most interesting, difficult, and significant issues in the theoretical phonetics of modern English has always been the study of phonetics. Apart from that this field concerning with how sounds are created, heard by other people, and how sounds interprets them are briefly explained in this article.*

Keywords : *Speech sounds, speech organs, linguistic signals, phonology, vocal cords, theories, substance, form, expressiveness.*

ФОНЕТИКА КАК ОТРАСЛЬ ЯЗЫКОЗНАНИЯ

Аннотация. *Данная статья посвящена теме «Фонетика как отрасль языкознания», так как одним из самых интересных, сложных и значимых вопросов теоретической фонетики современного английского языка всегда было изучение фонетики. с тем, как создаются звуки, которые слышат другие люди, и как звуки их интерпретируют, кратко объясняется в этой статье.*

Ключевые слова: *звуки речи, органы речи, языковые сигналы, фонология, голосовые связи, теории, субстанция, форма, выразительность.*

Speech sounds are the physical manifestation of language, which has been called "the most significant means of human intercourse." In order to exist, something must be spoken. The main method of language-based communication is oral speech. Written communication is secondary; it simply summarizes what is said orally [2].

The speech could be written or spoken. The word "phonetics" is derived from the Greek words "pho:n" and "-tica," which both signify sound and study. Thus, phonetics is a special branch of science that focuses on the phonetic structure and expressions of language. Other branches of linguistics, such as grammar (morphology and syntax), lexicology (vocabulary, the formation and meaning of words), and stylistics, describe the linguistic form and content (expressive emotional meaning). Human speech is the outcome of a very intricate chain of circumstances. The speaker's brain, or at a level related to language, is where the concept is formed;

Initially, linguistic signals were thought to be made up of a number of units that might be further classified as significant and non-significant. The link between each of a language's individual components, known as units or elements, can be understood in terms of a variety of concepts, ranging from sounds to morphemes to words to word combinations to phrases. A large number of concepts must be explained in terms of a perfectly planned and highly structured system, or the relationship between the units, when studying a language scientifically. A language system is made up of all of the relationships between linguistic elements. The nature of a system or how it functions explains how a language is structured. Each language has a unique set of rules and rules.

Phonetics is the study of the human sounds that actualize or give voice to a concept. It examines the characteristics of these sounds, how they are combined, and how they relate to

meaning. Phonetics is the study of a language's syllabic structure, segmental phonemes, word stress, and intonation.

The expressiveness level is its main focus. However, phonetics must also analyze the content since, at any point in the analysis, a considerable portion of the phonetician's interest is with the impact the expression unit under examination and its many qualities have on meaning.

The science of phonetics, at least in theory, is only concerned with those sounds produced by a human vocal apparatus that are or may be providers of organized information of language. Speech is only considered to consist of meaningful sound sequences.

Phonetics is crucial to the study of language as a result. It is necessary to comprehend it in order to have a sufficient comprehension of how language functions. No type of linguistic study can be conducted without taking the expression level content into consideration.

This means that phonetics is a foundational or fundamental component of linguistics, which is why it claims to be equally important to grammar and lexicon. Phonology and the study of the substance that conveys the code are the two primary subfields of phonetics. Phonology is the study of language sound patterns and how spoken language acts as a "code." It demonstrates the close connection between language and thought. In contemporary linguistics, the concepts of distinctions—substance and form—are used to describe this relationship. By "substance," we refer to the raw components of all linguistic components, and by "form," we refer to linguistic ideas. The "phonic material" in which linguistic forms manifest in human speech is known as the above.[4]

We could call this stage psychological. The speech organs receive the message that was created in the brain and delivered via the neurological system. The behavior of the articulating organs is therefore controlled by the human brain, which results in the production of a certain pattern of speech sounds. This second phase could be referred to as physiological. Sound waves are created when the speech equipment moves, which disrupts the airflow. Therefore, the third level may be referred to as physical or acoustic. Any form of communication also needs a listener in addition to a speaker. The receipt of sound waves by the listener's hearing, the transmission of the spoken word through the neurological system to the brain, and the linguistic interpretation of the information provided are therefore the final phases [5].

The following groups of speech organs can be based primarily on how they function in language: The primary requirement for producing speech sounds is air flow, which is given by the vocabulary or power mechanism. The bronchi, windpipe, and lungs together make up this mechanism. The energy that the power mechanism controls. The lungs alter the strength of spoken sounds by controlling the air wave's force. Dynamic stress and syllabic pulses have a direct impact on how the muscles that engage this system behave.

The air stream passes from the lungs through the wind pipe and into the vocal tract's upper stages. It first passes to the larynx, which contains the voice cords. The vocal cords' purpose is to act as a vibrator that is set in motion by the air stream that is sent from the lungs. It should be mentioned that the voice cords can vibrate in at least two different ways.

The vocal cords' role in voice production is their most significant speech-related function. When the vocal cords are brought together and vibrate under the pressure of the air leaving the lungs, the effect of voice is produced. The glottis is the term for the opening between the vocal cords. The glottis is forced to open by compressed air, which then causes the air pressure to drop, allowing the vocal cords to unite and causing the vibration.

The frequency of the vibrations affects the height of the speaking voice. The pitch rises as the vocal cords vibrate more frequently. The stream passes from the larynx to the pharynx, mouth, and nasal cavities. These Cavities' forms change the note generated in the larynx, resulting in specific speaking sounds.[1]

There are four main categories of phonetics that can be identified:

1.Special phonetics focuses on the analysis of a concrete language's phonetic system. When studying the phonological system in its static state during a specific time (synchronically, we speak about descriptive phonetics). We refer to historical, or evolutionary phonetics when the system is examined in the context of its historical development (diachronically).

Philological research is used in historical phonetics. It examines written records and contrasts how one word was spelled and pronounced during several periods in the language's history[2].

2. General Phonetics, which examines how people may make sounds, how their speech organs work, and how these factors are applied across all languages to produce speech sounds, syllables, stress, and intonation. This topic falls under general linguistics.

3. Descriptive phonetics investigates a language's phonetic system. As an illustration, consider English and Uzbek phonetics.

4. Historical or diachronic phonetics, which examines the changes a sound goes through as a language or set of languages develops.

5. Comparison-based phonetics. It investigates the phonetic characteristics of two or more languages with various phonological systems, like English, Russian, Uzbek, etc. It is a component of comparative linguistic typology.

As we've already mentioned, speech sounds are the physical manifestation of language, which is "the most important means of human contact." In order to exist, something must be spoken.

Language is made up of some units, which are further classified as major and non-significant. A language system is made up of all of the relationships between linguistic elements. In terms of systems and structures, languages vary.[3]

To conclude,The topic of "Phonetics as a branch of linguistics " focus of this paper. Phonetics is study of human sounds that give idea form or make it audible .It examines the characteristics of these sounds ,how they are combined and how they relate to meaning. Today , this theme is one of the most fascinating, disputable, and crucial issues of theoretical phonetics of modern English.

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